

MICROMECHANICS OF THE INTERFACE IN POLYMER COMPOSITES - CAPABILITIES AND LIMITATIONS OF THE COMMON TEST METHODS

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ABSTRACT

The stress fields arising in the pull-out test and in the indentation test are analysed by means of the finite element method. It is shown that a mixed-mode failure arises in the interface and that the common interpretation of the test data is not reasonable. Experimental results of pull-out tests reveal that the failure of the interface starts long before the force maximum is reached. Furthermore, a simulation of the fracture process arising in the single fiber pull-out test is given.

INTRODUCTION

The common micromechanical test techniques for the determination of the adhesive strength in polymer composites, such as the pull-out, the indentation and the fragmentation test, only provide one intergral quantity, e.g. the failure load, and no detailed information about the stress distribution in the interface is given. There are two ways for the evaluation of the micromechanical test data, which are differing in general. The first one is the stress based evaluation, this is, the maximum stresses arising in the interface in the moment of total failure are determined theoretically [1-3]. The second way is the fracture mechanics based evaluation, e.g. the determination of an energy release rate. This procedure requires the measurement of the crack length, which is possible only in transparent matrices [5,6]. It will be discussed in section three on the example of the pull-out test.

The most frequently used procedure is the stress based determination of the adhesion in terms of an 'interfacial shear strength'. The necessary theoretical stress analysis usually is performed employing strongly simplified 'data reduction schemes', even though the stress field near the interface is very complex [1-3, 7]. When the adhesive strength data, calculated from different types of tests, are compared, significant differences are found. This should not really be surprising, because the stress distributions arising in the respective tests are different and, furthermore, depend on several parameters.

Since the complete analytical solution of the respective boundary value problems is not available, two different types of simplified approaches are widely used. The first one is based on a shear lag model [1-4], presuming a linear-elastic matrix. In addition to the idealisations of the material behaviour, further assumptions concerning the stress field are introduced. However, because these

assumptions are inconsistent within the linear theory of elasticity, the results obtained using this model are of low value [8,9]. The second approach is based on the yielding behaviour of the polymer matrices, assuming constant shear stresses to act along the whole interface, resulting in the well known Kelly-Tyson formula. This hypothesis implies an unlimited yielding of the matrix, which results in unrealistic strains due to the strong stress and strain gradients arising around the interface, especially near the fiber entry.

An alternative tool for the stress analysis is the finite element method. The finite element analysis gives an approximate solution of the respective boundary value problem, which is consistent within the respective material theory. The accuracy of the solution can be controlled by the fineness of the element mesh. In the following, the finite element method is used to calculate the stress field arising in the pull-out and in the indentation test. By comparison of the stress distributions, the different failure modes arising in these tests are shown. In addition, the interfacial fracture process is simulated for the pull-out test and the energy release rate is calculated.

1. FINITE ELEMENT MODELS OF THE MICROMECHANICAL TESTS

Within the theory of elasticity, stress singularities arise at corners of interfaces in two phase materials, this is at fiber ends (pull-out test) or at the matrix surface (pull-out test, indentation test). In real materials, the theoretical singularities are transformed to stress concentrations. In plasticising materials, the stress concentrations are decreased due to the loss of stiffness during the yielding process on the expense of strongly increasing strains. This means that the failure still may occur in those zones, where the elastic stress concentrations arise, by reaching the limit strain. This is, despite of a potential plasticising of the polymer matrices, the investigation of the elastic fields is meaningful since it reveals the essential characteristics of the interfacial loading. For the sake of clearness, this paper is confined to a linear-elastic analysis of the tests.

In the present paper, the analysis is performed for a combination of E-glass fibers embedded in a polycarbonate matrix, exhibiting a stiffness ratio of 32 and a fiber length to diameter ratio of 15 (Fig. 1). In order to minimise the influence of the mesh on the results, the same element mesh is used in the critical zone in both models. In the pull-out test, however, the model is enhanced by a pure matrix region beyond the fiber end and by a short part of fiber rising above the matrix surface.

Figure 1. Sketch of the pull-out (a) and indentation model (b)

The load is applied via prescribed displacements, which are normalised in order to give rise to the same maximum fiber force in each system. In the pull-out model, the displacement is applied to the fiber rising above the matrix, while in the indentation model, the fiber is loaded by a flat indenter with a smoothed edge and a stiffness corresponding to a diamond. At the bottom of the models, fixed displacement boundary conditions are prescribed.

2. STRESS DISTRIBUTION IN THE FIBER AND IN THE INTERFACE

Apart from the loading direction there are two further differences between the pull-out and the indentation test. The first one is the fact that pull-out tests usually are performed on specimens, consisting of single fibers embedded in a pure matrix region, while indentation tests are conducted on real composites. According to the actual tests, the finite element model of the pull-out test considers a pure matrix surrounding, while the indentation model considers a composite with 60% fiber volume fraction, which represents a common value. The second difference is the way the load is applied. While in the pull-out test the load is applied far away from the fiber entry, an additional perturbation of the stress field is inferred by the indenter in the indentation test. In order to obtain an insight into the inherent differences between the two tests, an indentation test for the same conditions, i.e. for a zero fiber volume fraction is analysed. This system, on the other hand, can also be regarded as a limit case to study the influence of the fiber volume fraction.

The axial stresses arising in the center of the loaded fibers decrease with a decreasing slope from the matrix surface in both tests (Fig. 2). In the indentation test, however, the decay within a zone of about one fiber diameter is very high, irrespective of the fiber volume fraction. This is the result of a redistribution of the stresses, which are concentrated in the center of the fiber due to the indenter. Beyond this zone, the influence of the fiber volume fraction becomes obvious. The stresses are almost completely transferred into the neighbouring material in case of the composite, while about 15% of the external force remains in the fiber in case of the pure matrix surrounding. In the pull-out test, the decrease of the axial stresses is less inhomogeneous, since no stress perturbation due to the load application arises.

Figure 2. Axial fiber stresses for the pull-out and indentation test

In both tests, the interfacial shear stresses are distributed very inhomogeneously (Fig. 3a). The stresses near the matrix surface are plotted in detail in Fig. 3b for convenience. In this region, a severe stress concentration arises, followed by a rapid decay. In the indentation test, the stress maximum does not occur directly at the matrix surface but somewhat below. This is a result of the perturbation of the stress field due to the indenter. The stress maximum in case of a pure matrix surrounding is about 30% lower compared with the composite material. The diminution of the interfacial shear stresses

indicates that the stress transfer into the neighbouring material is decreased as a result of the reduced stiffness. Since the interfacial shear stress distribution depends on the fiber volume fraction, indentation tests should be performed using similar fiber contents. While the stresses level off up to the fiber end in the indentation test, they increase again near the fiber end in the pull-out test, where a second maximum of lower intensity arises. The ratio of the maxima in the pull-out test, however, strongly depends on the stiffness ratio and on the length to diameter ratio of the fiber. In case of very short and stiff fibers, e.g. HM carbon fibers, the maximum at the fiber end is dominating [8,9].

Figure 3. Interfacial shear stresses for the pull-out and indentation test ; a: total system, b: detail

In addition to the shear stresses, high interfacial radial stresses are active in a small zone of less than one fiber radius near the matrix surface (Fig. 4). The intensity of the radial stresses is more than two times that of the corresponding shear stresses. They are nearly independent of the fiber volume fraction in the indentation test. While in the latter test compressive stresses occur, tensile stresses are active in the pull-out test. This means that completely different kinds of failure arise in these tests. In the pull-out test, a mixed-mode failure with predominating mode I arises, while in the indentation test a mode II failure occurs, superimposed by compressive radial stresses. As a result of the compressive stresses, a further stress transfer after debonding can take place by frictional stresses. It has to be noted that most of the shear lag based analyses do not take into account the existence of radial stresses and, accordingly, assume a pure mode II failure to occur.

Figure 4. Interfacial radial stresses for the pull-out and indentation test

As a consequence of the different failure modes arising in the pull-out and in the indentation test, the failure occurs at different external loads even though the actual strength of the interface is the same. This is, if the 'interfacial shear strength' is calculated, based on the force maximum, different levels of adhesion are found. Therefore, it is not reasonable to calculate an 'interfacial shear strength' but a failure criterion has to be used instead, taking into account the effect of multiaxial stresses. In general, a certain variation of the mode ratio can be achieved using both tests by varying the length to diameter ratio in the pull out test as well as the fiber content in the indentation test. However, the range of the mode ratios is narrow and a scatter due to the different sample preparation processes is introduced.

3. FRACTURE MECHANICAL BASED EVALUATION OF THE TEST DATA

The determination of the adhesion based on the 'interfacial shear strength' utilises the force maximum and deduces the corresponding stresses theoretically. This implies the assumption that the failure process starts when the force maximum is reached and then propagates in a catastrophic fashion. In order to proof this assumption, the pull-out process is studied under a microscope using flat specimens, i.e. the matrix is bounded by two glass plates [6]. In order to allow a stable crack propagation, a very stiff testing device was built, using a piezo translator and a piezo force cell mounted on a very strong frame. Since the free fiber length, which is the distance between the matrix surface and the clamping, is the most compliant part in the testing system, this length was reduced to 30 to 50 microns.

With this device, pull-out tests on glass fibers embedded in several transparent matrices, e.g. polystyrene and polycarbonate, were conducted. Two main features were found. The first is the fact that indeed a stable crack propagation is observable over a range of 60% to 80% of the embedded fiber length. The second is that a change of the slope in the force-displacement trace can be detected after crack initiation. This effect is more pronounced in case of a rather brittle matrix like polystyrene (Fig. 5), where the trace is almost linear, whereas a rather nonlinear behaviour is encountered in case of a polycarbonate matrix.

Figure 5. Force-displacement trace of the pull-out test for a glass fiber - polystyrene matrix

These results show that the crack initiation occurs long before the ultimate load is reached. After the crack has started, the load is further increased. This is a consequence of the frictional shear stresses, which are active in the debonded interface. As a result, the stress field at the crack tip is not governed by the total external force but by the external force minus the frictional force in the interface. However, even if low friction would arise in the interface, the force would not drop to zero immediately, because the stress field at the crack tip does not change significantly during the first phase of

the crack propagation. This leads to an only slowly increasing energy release rate, as shown later. From these results, we can conclude the following:

- the evaluation of the maximum force in order to determine an 'interfacial shear strength' is not reasonable, since this is not representative for the maximum interfacial stresses
- the measurement of the crack length during the failure process in general allows the calculation of a mixed mode energy release rate as a parameter characterising the adhesion of the interface in case of transparent matrices

Especially the first conclusion makes the common interpretation of the pull-out test data doubtful. The calculated 'shear strength' depends on the friction in the debonded interface and can, therefore, not be regarded as a parameter characterising the bond strength between fiber and matrix. If still an interfacial failure stress is desired, not the maximum force but the force in the moment of crack initiation has to be used. If a non-transparent matrix is considered, the kink in the force displacement trace indicates this point. However, in case of a rather nonlinear material behaviour of the matrix, this point is hard to detect, making the evaluation problematical. The fracture mechanical approach, on the other hand, requires a transparent matrix for the measurement of the crack length and a time consuming specimen preparation.

FINITE ELEMENT CALCULATION OF THE ENERGY RELEASE RATE

In order to gain some insight into the fracture process, a finite element simulation of the crack propagation is performed and the released energy as well as the radial and shear stress intensities at the crack tip are calculated for a glass fiber-polycarbonate matrix system. The critical energy release rate characterises the fracture toughness of a material and is equivalent to the critical stress intensity factor or the J-integral in linear elasticity. If a perfectly elastic material is presumed, the energy release rate during crack propagation only depends on the change of the stress field at the crack tip.

The same kind of problem arising in the failure stress analysis is also encountered in the fracture mechanical evaluation. Due to the superposition of the stresses at the crack tip, only a mixed-mode energy release rate can be determined. In Fig.6 the energy release rate is plotted versus the crack length under 'fixed load' conditions for a frictionless interface. The energy release rate increases slowly beyond a small minimum directly after the crack initiation, which is caused by a redistribution of the crack tip stresses, as discussed later. This shows that already a small friction in the debonded zone leads to a stable crack propagation. If the crack approaches the fiber end, the energy release rate dramatically increases, leading to an unstable crack extension, even in case of high friction.

Figure 6. Energy release rate during interfacial crack propagation in the pull-out test

The slow increase of the energy release rate during the first phase of the crack can be explained considering the stress intensities at the crack tip (Fig. 7). Before the crack starts, the radial stresses exceed the shear stresses. This is, the failure is caused by mode I stresses. Within a short period of the crack extension, the mode ratio changes to prevailing mode II. Both stress components only slightly increase during the further crack propagation until the crack approaches the fiber end. Here, both stresses increase steeply, resulting in the dramatical growth of the energy release rate.

Figure 7. Shear and radial stress intensities at the crack tip in the pull-out test

The 'fixed loads' condition represents the most critical case concerning the stability of the crack. If pull-out tests are displacement driven, a more or less 'fixed grips' condition is given, depending on the compliance of the testing device. In order to get an estimation of the stability of the crack, an experiment is simulated, where the displacement is prescribed in such a way that the same energy release rate is produced by the propagating crack, independent of the position of the crack tip. This is, the critical energy release G_c rate is assumed to be constant over the whole crack length. The analysis is performed for different compliances of the testing system, represented by a variation of the free fiber length, i.e. the distance between the clamp and the matrix surface (Fig. 8).

Figure 8. Applied displacements for constant energy release rate G_c

First, the system with a free fiber length of one fiber diameter, i.e. 10 microns, is studied. In the beginning of the crack, the displacement increases reaching a small maximum. This is the point, where the energy release rate for 'fixed loads' exhibits a minimum. Beyond this maximum, the displacement has to be decreased in order to produce a constant G_c value, until a minimum is reached at a crack length of about three fiber radii. However, in actual tests, the displacement is not

driven back but it is increased or held constant. This means that, neglecting dynamical effects, the crack runs unstably from the first displacement maximum until this value is met again. Now, the displacement can be further increased while the crack propagates stably until the second maximum near the fiber end is reached. At this point, the catastrophic failure of the interface occurs. The traces for a free fiber length of 40 and 100 diameters show that the stable phase of the crack is significantly decreased if the compliance is increased. In case of a free fiber length of 100 diameters, the crack even extends unstably after reaching the first displacement maximum. Although these calculations utilise an idealised model, not taking into account the whole complexity of the failure process in an actual test, they reveal, that the compliance plays an important role and, furthermore, that a stable crack can not be observed in very compliant devices, if the interfacial friction is low.

CONCLUSIONS

The finite element analyses of the the pull-out and indentation test reveal some interesting features:

- the failure initiation in the pull-out test is governed by mode I stresses
- during the fracture process, the mode ratio changes to a prevailing mode II
- the evaluation of the force maximum arising in the pull-out test is not reasonable in case of friction
- a stable crack propagation can be achieved in the pull-out test by the use of a stiff testing device, allowing the determination of an energy release rate in case of transparent matrices
- in the indentation test, a mode II failure superimposed by compressive radial stresses is occurs.

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